

Resolution of dicyanobis(biguanidinium)cobalt(III) chloride

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cis-Dicyanobis(biguanidinium)cobalt(III) salts have been prepared and the complex chloride has been resolved into optically active diastereoisomers, as tartrate salt, using equivalent amount of silver *d*-tartrate. All the fractions showed a constant dextro rotation. The laevo form could not be isolated probably due to the conversion of laevo to dextro form occurs during crystallization. The reason of conversion of one form to the other and structures of complexes have been discussed.

Trisbiguanidinium as well as disubstituted bis(biguanidinium)cobalt(III) and rhodium(III) complexes have been studied extensively and some of their *cis* complexes have been resolved into their optically active antipode¹⁻³. Most of the active antipodes have been stabilized as their *d*-tartrate and camphor-*d*-sulphonate salts. The specific property of certain geometric conformation of complexes aroused considerable interest towards isolation and characterization of coordination complexes in pure optically active form. In the present investigation, dicyanobis(biguanidinium)cobalt(III) salts have been prepared and its complex tartrate has been resolved into its optically active antipode and it has been found to remain stable in dextro form only.

Results and discussion

The complex $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3]_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ undergoes ligand substitution reaction when treated with strong ligand like CN^- . The dicyano complex $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_2(\text{CN})_2]^+$ which has been obtained in *cis*-form only, while $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{CN})_2]^+$ which has been obtained both in *cis* and *trans* isomers. The dicyano complex has been obtained as chloride, nitrate, sulphate and tartrate. The *d*-tartrate of complex has been found to be optically active and it is isolated exclusively as *d* form⁴⁻⁷. The molar optical rotation recorded by polarimeter has been found to be $[\text{M}]_D = 1510.53^\circ$.

The molar conductance values of dicyano complex chloride in (M/32) and (M/1024) solution were found to be 102 and 113 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2$. The value indicated it to be 1 : 1 electrolyte. The molar conductance of complex tartrate ($\lambda_m = 132 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) indicated it to be 1 : 1 electrolyte. The complex was found to be diamagnetic indicating its oxidation state +3. The electronic absorption spectra of the complex showed two bands at 27570 and 20833 cm^{-1} . The ϵ_{max} value of these complexes were found in the range of ~280 and 180 indicating *d-d* transition. The electronic transition of the complex chloride has been assigned as,

${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{2g}$ transitions respectively.

The IR spectra of complex chloride and complex tartrate were recorded as KBr disc. The broad IR bands observed around 3250–2950 cm^{-1} for all the complexes indicated H-bonded H_2O , $-\text{NH}_2$ and $>\text{NH}$ groups in the complexes⁸. A band of medium intensity observed at 2100 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of coordinated CN^- group in the complex⁹. The broad and strong band near 1630 cm^{-1} in the complex is assigned to NH_2 and NH vibrations^{3a}.

Experimental

Biguanide (BigH^+) was prepared by heating dicyandiamide and ammonium iodide as reported in literature¹⁰. The dicyanobis(biguanidinium)cobalt(III) salts were prepared by ligand substitution reaction from tris(biguanidinium)cobalt(III) salt using aqueous KCN.

About 6 g biguanidium sulphate ($\text{BigH}^+\text{HSO}_4$) was dissolved in cold 50 ml (2%) aqueous solution of NaOH and treated with an aqueous solution of 2.80 g of $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (3 : 1 molar ratio) with constant stirring when cream yellow bis(biguanidium)cobalt(II) base separated immediately. The product was mixed with 2 g active charcoal and air was bubbled through it for two hours, when the cream yellow base dissolved gradually yielding orange yellow solution. The solution was neutralized with dilute H_2SO_4 (pH 3–4) and concentrated on steam bath to half of its volume. The solution was left overnight in a refrigerator when orange-yellow tris-chelated complex, $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3]_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was separated. The complex was washed with cold water and ethanol and dried in air (yield 90%).

About 3 g of above tris complex was dissolved in 30 ml water and treated with 2 g KCN and the mixed solution was heated on a steam bath for half an hour when colour of solution changed from orange to light yellow. The solution

was concentrated and cooled when light yellow crystalline complex separated. It was filtered and washed thoroughly with cold ethanol and dried in air (yield 90%).

About 2 g of complex sulphate was dissolved in 20 ml hot water and treated with molar proportion of aqueous solution of $BaCl_2$ solution. The white precipitate of $BaSO_4$ separated was filtered and the clear filtrate was concentrated and cooled when yellow needle shaped crystals separated gradually. The product was collected on a filter paper washed with water and dried in air.

About 2 g complex chloride was dissolved in 30 ml water and silver salt of *d*-tartaric acid (1.5 g) was added to it. The resulting solution was filtered and concentrated to about 10 ml and cooled when yellow precipitate separated gradually (yield 80%).

The precipitate was dissolved in 10 ml hot water and filtered. The filtrate on crystallization yielded flat crystals. The optical activity of compound was measured after each crystallization. The crystallized complex was always found to show rotation of plane polarized light in right (dextro form). The attempt to isolate *l*-form could not succeed and even meso complex was not resolved. The attempt to isolate optically active complex chloride or sulphate salt was unsuccessful. The analytical results were found close to those of the formula suggested for the complex.

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